
CISA Case: CCASE0145741 Opened

1 message

CISA Service Desk <utsprod@servicenowservices.com>
Reply-to: CISA Service Desk <utsprod@servicenowservices.com>
To: Phunky.pharmacology@gmail.com

Mon, Dec 15, 2025 at 2:40 PM

Thank you for your submission to CISA. Case number CCASE0145741 has been generated. Should you need to share any additional information related to this case, please reply to this email.

CISA will review this case and if additional information is required we will contact you.

If this case involves an incident report, please provide the outcome of the incident to include the root cause and resolution when available.

NCISS Score:

Thank you,
CISA Service Desk
Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA)
844-Say-CISA (729-2472)
contact@cisa.dhs.gov
<http://www.cisa.gov>

Ref:MSG0585296_kOK8PBUfoEXSbDkHe59z